

ANALYTICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THERMAL AND DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports some recent findings in the investigation of physical properties of woven fabric composites. The primary focus is on the analytical prediction of effective thermal conductivities and dielectric properties. Closed-form solutions of the transverse effective thermal conductivity of 4-harness satin fabric composites and the in-plane effective dielectric properties of plain weave fabric composites are presented. Excellent agreement is found between present predictions and existing results in the open literature.

INTRODUCTION

Significant advancement has been made in recent years in industrial applications of woven fabric composites. The elastic and strength behavior of woven fabric composites has been studied extensively (See for example Ref. [1]). Limited studies have been made concerning their thermal and electrical properties [2 - 5]. Ning and Chou [6, 7] recently performed an analytical study of the transverse and in-plane effective thermal conductivities of plain weave fabric composites. Analytical models for determining the effective properties have been developed based on the unit cell structure of composites and thermal-electrical analogy. Closed-form solutions with general applicability have been obtained.

This study focuses on the analytical characterization of the transverse effective thermal conductivity of 4-harness satin fabric composites and in-plane effective dielectric properties of plain weave fabric composites. The microstructure of 4-harness fabric composites is modeled following the technique developed in Refs. [6 and 7]. The transverse effective thermal conductivity of the composites is predicted using the thermal-electrical analogy. The in-plane effective dielectric constants of plain weave fabric composites are determined from the closed-form solutions of in-plane effective thermal conductivities of the same composites utilizing the analogy between heat conduction and electrostatics. The in-plane effective loss factors and loss tangents of the composites are derived based on the theory of Schulgasser and Hashin [8]. Finally, numerical examples are given to illustrate applications of the solutions.

TRANSVERSE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF 4-HARNESS SATIN FABRIC COMPOSITES

Four-harness satin fabrics, also known as claw foot satin or Turkish satin, are often used in composites. The microstructure of a composite reinforced with 4-harness satin fabric is shown schematically in Fig. 1. The region enclosed by the dotted lines indicates the unit cell. The weft and warp yarn materials and their dimensions are assumed to be identical.

Figure 1. Interlacing pattern in 4-harness satin fabric lamina

Further, the unit cell of Fig. 1 can be idealized as that shown in Fig. 2. A yarn impregnated with a matrix material is simulated as a transversely isotropic unidirectional composite with the fibers inclined at a piecewise mean angle with respect to the reference axis. The transverse thermal conductivities of the yarns are determined using unidirectional composite analysis, and then the transverse effective thermal conductivity of the composite is derived based on the unit cell model. In this study, the thermal-electrical analogy is adopted, which is based on the similarity between the governing differential equations in heat and electrical conductions. Thus the effective thermal conductivity can be analyzed using a thermal resistance model.

Figure 2. Idealized unit cell of 4-harness satin fabric lamina

The unit cell in Fig. 2 can be partitioned into eleven thermally conductive elements (denoted by 1, 2, 3, ..., 11) situated in parallel (Fig. 3). Based on the partition, the corresponding thermal resistance network can be readily constructed, and the equivalent thermal resistance R of the unit cell is expressed as

$$\frac{1}{R} = 4 \frac{1}{R_1} + 6 \frac{1}{R_2} + 4 \frac{1}{R_3} + 6 \frac{1}{R_4} + 8 \frac{1}{R_5} + 6 \frac{1}{R_6} + 6 \frac{1}{R_7} + 6 \frac{1}{R_8}$$

$$+ 6 \frac{1}{R_9} + 3 \frac{1}{R_{10}} + 4 \frac{1}{R_{11}} \quad (1)$$

where R_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 11$) is the equivalent thermal resistance of the i -th element.

Figure 3. Partition of conductive elements of the unit cell

The elements in Fig. 3 can be further divided into sub-elements. Figures 4 and 5 give, for example, the divisions of elements 1 and 11, and the corresponding thermal resistance networks. The thermal resistance r of each conductive sub-element is determined by

$$r = \frac{L}{kA} \quad (2)$$

where L and k are, respectively, the length and effective thermal conductivity in the heat flux direction of the sub-element under consideration, and A is the cross-sectional area perpendicular to the direction of heat flux. Then, the equivalent thermal resistances of elements 1 and 11 can be obtained as follows:

Figure 4. Partition (a) and thermal resistance network (b) of element 1

Figure 5. Partition (a) and thermal resistance network (b) of element 11

$$\frac{1}{R_1} = 2ag \left(\frac{h + h_m}{k_m} + \frac{h - h_m}{k_1} \right)^{-1} + \frac{a^2}{4} \left(\frac{h_m}{k_m} + \frac{h - h_m}{k_2} \right)^{-1} + g^2 \left(\frac{h}{k_m} \right)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{R_{11}} = ag \left(\frac{h + h_m}{k_m} + \frac{h - h_m}{k_2} \right)^{-1} + g^2 \left(\frac{h}{k_m} \right)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where k_m is the thermal conductivity of the matrix; k_1 and k_2 are, respectively, the transverse thermal conductivities of the yarns with fibers inclined at piecewise mean angles $\bar{\theta}_1$ and $\bar{\theta}_2$; h is the thickness of the unit cell.

The equivalent thermal resistance R of the unit cell is related to the transverse effective thermal conductivity of the 4-harness satin fabric composite, k_e , by

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{16k_e(a+g)^2}{h} \quad (5)$$

Substituting the equivalent thermal resistance of all elements and Eqn (5) into Eqn (1), the transverse effective thermal conductivity of 4-harness satin fabric composites can be obtained as

$$k_e = \frac{k_m}{\left(1 + \frac{g}{a}\right)^2} \left[\frac{1}{\frac{h_m}{h} \left(1 - \frac{k_m}{k_2}\right) + \frac{k_m}{k_2}} + 2 \frac{\frac{g}{a}}{\frac{h_m}{h} \left(1 - \frac{k_m}{k_2}\right) + \left(1 + \frac{k_m}{k_2}\right)} + 2 \frac{\frac{g}{a}}{\frac{h_m}{h} \left(1 - \frac{k_m}{k_1}\right) + \left(1 + \frac{k_m}{k_1}\right)} + \left(\frac{g}{a}\right)^2 \right] \quad (6)$$

where k_1 , k_2 , and $\frac{h_m}{h}$ can be evaluated by Eqns (12) - (15) and (17) as shown in Ref. [6].

IN-PLANE DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF PLAIN WEAVE FABRIC COMPOSITES

Following the method described in Section 2, the in-plane effective thermal conductivities of plain weave fabric composites has been obtained [7]. Owing to the analogy between heat conduction and electrostatics, this solution technique is also applicable to the evaluation of in-plane dielectric constants of the fabric composites. Further, the in-plane effective loss factors and effective loss tangents can be determined based on the theory of Schulgasser and Hashin [8]. The solution of the effective dielectric constant can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon'_{iew} = & \epsilon'_m \frac{h_m}{h} + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{h_m}{h}\right) \cdot \left\{ \frac{\frac{g}{a}}{1 + \frac{g}{a}} \epsilon'_m + \frac{g}{a} \left(\epsilon'_{f1}{}^{-1} + \frac{g}{a} \epsilon'_m{}^{-1} \right) \right. \\ & + \left. \left[\epsilon'_{f2}{}^{-1} + \frac{g}{a} \left(\frac{1}{2} \epsilon'_m + (\epsilon'_m{}^{-1} + \epsilon'_{w1}{}^{-1}) \right)^{-1} \right]^{-1} \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\epsilon'_{w2}{}^{-1} + \frac{g}{a} \left(\frac{1}{2} \epsilon'_{w1} + (\epsilon'_{w1}{}^{-1} + \epsilon'_m{}^{-1}) \right)^{-1} \right]^{-1} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where ϵ'_m is the matrix dielectric constant, ϵ'_{d1} and ϵ'_{d2} are, respectively, transverse dielectric constants of the yarns with the fibers inclined at the piecewise mean angles $\bar{\theta}_{d1}$ and $\bar{\theta}_{d2}$; h_m and h are thicknesses of the matrix and the plain weave fabric lamina, respectively; a and g are yarn width and gap width between two neighboring yarns. The parameters ϵ'_{wi} and ϵ'_{fi} ($i = 1, 2$) are determined by

$$\epsilon'_{wi} = \epsilon'_a \cos^2 \bar{\theta}_{wi} + \epsilon'_t \sin^2 \bar{\theta}_{wi} \quad (8)$$

$$\epsilon'_{fi} = \epsilon'_t \quad (9)$$

In Eqn (8), ϵ'_a and ϵ'_t are, respectively, yarn axial and transverse dielectric constants. ϵ'_a is evaluated by

$$\epsilon'_a = c_{fp} \epsilon'_{fa} + (1 - c_{fp}) \epsilon'_m \quad (10)$$

where c_{fp} is fiber volume fraction of the yarns, and ϵ'_{fa} is fiber axial dielectric constant. ϵ'_t is given by the Clayton's equation [9]:

$$\epsilon'_t = \frac{\epsilon'_m}{4} \left[\sqrt{(1 - c_{fp})^2 \left(\frac{\epsilon'_{fr}}{\epsilon'_m} - 1 \right)^2 + \frac{4\epsilon'_{fr}}{\epsilon'_m}} - (1 - c_{fp}) \left(\frac{\epsilon'_{fr}}{\epsilon'_m} - 1 \right) \right]^2 \quad (11)$$

where ϵ'_{fr} is the fiber radial dielectric constant. $\bar{\theta}_{wi}$ ($i = 1, 2$) are fiber mean inclination angles. The loss factor ϵ''_{iew} is determined by

$$\epsilon''_{iew} = \frac{\partial \epsilon'_{iew}}{\partial \epsilon'_1} \epsilon''_1 + \frac{\partial \epsilon'_{iew}}{\partial \epsilon'_2} \epsilon''_2 \quad (12)$$

in which ϵ'_k and ϵ''_k ($k = 1, 2$) are, respectively, dielectric constants and loss factors of the constituent materials. Then, the loss tangent is given by

$$\tan \delta_{iew} = \epsilon''_{iew} / \epsilon'_{iew} \quad (13)$$

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, numerical examples are given to illustrate the applications of analytical solutions.

For the transverse effective thermal conductivity of 4-harness satin fabric composites, we consider E-glass reinforced epoxy. The relevant geometric and material parameters are: $g/a = 0.1$, $c_{fp} = 0.63$, $\bar{\theta}_i$ ($i = 1, 2$), $k_m = 0.19 \text{ W/m-K}$, $k_{fa} = k_{fr} = 1.03 \text{ W/m-K}$. The values of $\bar{\theta}_i$ are given in Table 1. The transverse effective thermal conductivities of the composites are depicted in Fig. 6.

Table 1. Fiber mean inclination angles of 4-harness satin composites*

Fiber volume fraction (%)	Piecewise mean inclination angles of fibers (degree)	
	$\bar{\theta}_{d1}$	$\bar{\theta}_{d2}$
22	22.01	3.7
25	20.43	3.44
28	19.63	3.31
30	18.03	3.05
33	17.23	2.91
36	16.82	2.84

* Based on the formula and parameters given in Ref. [2]

For the in-plane effective dielectric properties, we consider E-glass plain weave fabric lamina reinforced with polyimide. This composite system has been investigated by Agarwal [10]. The present predictions and Agarwal's results are given in Fig. 7.

CONCLUSIONS

Analytical solutions of the transverse effective thermal conductivities of 4-harness satin fabric composites and in-plane effective dielectric properties of plain weave fabric composites have been developed. The predictability of the solutions has been confirmed. Since only simple algebraic operations are involved, the techniques and models developed in this study could benefit the parametric study and design optimization of fabric composites.

Figure 6. Transverse effective thermal conductivities of 4-harness satin fabric laminae for E-glass/epoxy.

Figure 7. In-plane effective dielectric constants of plain weave fabric laminae for E-glass/polyimide (* Ref. [10]).

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